

Saving Database Copies to OCI Immutable Buckets

CERN openlab Project Report

Andrei Dorian Duma*¹ and Sebastien Masson†²

¹University Politehnica of Bucharest

²IT Databases & Analytics, CERN

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Abstract

Databases managed by CERN’s IT department are crucial for research operations. Although multiple mechanisms for data protection and availability already exist, these databases might still be vulnerable to ransomware attacks. In this report we describe the design and implementation of a tool that copies Oracle Database files to *immutable buckets*, a feature offered by Oracle’s Object Storage cloud service. The buckets’ time-based retention rules guarantee that an attacker cannot delete or modify backup files no matter the degree of access gained within CERN’s systems.

1 Introduction

The IT department at CERN oversees hundreds of databases used across the organization for storing experiment, administrative and other kinds of data. Many of these databases contain data that, if lost, would cause CERN significant harm. It is therefore essential that appropriate data protection measures are put in place. Indeed, multiple mechanisms already exist to protect data and ensure its availability for CERN applications.

Figure 1 shows an Oracle database in a typical setup: there is a primary database instance that serves application requests during normal operation; a secondary instance in a different datacenter receives all transactions performed on the primary database in real-time and is prepared to handle the application traffic in case the primary instance becomes unavailable; finally,

*andrei@dumco.ro

†sebastien.masson@cern.ch

periodic backups are created and stored on disk and tape to allow for data recovery if required. Although in this report we will concern ourselves with Oracle databases, similar machinery exists for other types of databases at CERN.

Figure 1: A typical Oracle database with backups and a secondary instance

We believe the mechanisms described above are not sufficient to ensure data protection in case of a security breach. Figure 2 shows the same system as above, highlighting its limitations.

Figure 2: Limitations of a database's backups and secondary instance

Although the secondary database provides data *availability*, it does not guarantee data protection. Since it mirrors the transactions performed on the primary database in real-time, it is bound to also replicate destructive operations. An attacker that deletes data on the primary database will therefore affect data on the secondary database as well.

The backups do contribute to data protection, but their security is hindered by the insufficient access boundaries of the Oracle tooling used to manage them. Backups in Oracle databases are created, cataloged, restored and deleted using RMAN¹. Although very well-suited for these tasks, RMAN sees all backups as belonging to one large realm and provides no safeguards against malicious access. For example, the following command deletes a database and all its backups, without even asking for confirmation!

```
RMAN> DROP DATABASE INCLUDING BACKUPS NOPROMPT;
```

To address these shortcomings, we propose periodically sending copies of a database’s files somewhere outside of RMAN’s control. Oracle’s Object Storage² offers immutable buckets³, “governed by time-bound retention rules that protect data from modification or deletion for a specified duration”. Once a retention rule comes into effect, not even an administrator can delete files uploaded to such a bucket.

Figure 3: Sending database files outside of RMAN’s control

In order to make backups to immutable buckets accessible to database administrators in the IT department, we implemented the `cloud_backup` command-line tool, which uploads the essential files of an Oracle database to an OCI bucket. This tool is also able to list, download and delete existing

¹Oracle reference and guide.

²Oracle Object Storage product page.

³Official guide on how to use immutable buckets.

backups (called *cloud backups* from this point). We continue with presenting the design and implementation of this tool, beginning with the technical context for which it was developed.

2 Technical Context

An Oracle database works with in-memory data structures as well as files persisted on disk. For backup and recovery purposes we are interested in the files, each of them belonging to one of three important classes:

- Every Oracle Database has a **control file**⁴, which is a small binary file that records the physical structure and state of the database (file locations, sequence numbers, checkpoint information and more).
- **Data files**⁵ are physical files of the operating system that store the data of all logical structures in the database.
- Another crucial structure for recovery operations is the redo log⁶, which consists of two or more groups of preallocated files that store all changes made to the database as they occur. Oracle Database allows saving filled groups of redo log files (**archived logs**) to one or more offline destinations, known collectively as the *archived redo log*⁶.

In order to create a cloud backup for a database, a sufficient set of these files needs to be collected and uploaded to the OCI bucket. Despite all of them being simply files on disk, they cannot be collected by the same method:

- The **control file** is better generated dynamically using a dedicated RMAN command.
- In a typical database setup at CERN, **data files** reside on multiple network-attached disks (NAS volumes). These volumes use filesystem snapshots to facilitate certain operations. The data files we send to the cloud are collected from these snapshots.

An alternative approach here would be to ask the Oracle database to prepare a set of backup files and upload those. Although this process offers certain desirable consistency guarantees, it takes a long time to complete for large databases and requires sending many more archive logs to the cloud to achieve consistency at recovery time (at least those logs produced during the creation of the backup). Conversely, filesystem snapshots copy the database instantaneously regardless of its size.

⁴Oracle documentation: „What is a control file?“

⁵Oracle: „About Data Files“

⁶Oracle: „What Is the Redo Log?“ and „What Is the Archived Redo Log?“

Since multiple snapshots exist for each given volume (taken at different times), we need to choose the „best” set of snapshots available across all volumes. To minimize a backup’s recovery time, the „best” snapshot set is the most recent one whose snapshots were all taken within a short-enough time interval.

- Since **archived logs** are not modified after they are written to disk, we can simply upload them directly. Still, in order to minimize the backup size, we still need to select as few archive logs as possible. We will upload just enough archive logs to „clear datafile fuzziness”⁷.

Figure 4 illustrates how a database’s underlying files might be structured on disk.

Figure 4: A database’s underlying control file, data files & archive logs

It is in this context that we developed the command-line tool `cloud_backup`. In the next section we describe the inner workings of this tool and how users interact with it.

3 Design and Implementation

The `cloud_backup` tool uses filesystem snapshots to create stand-alone backups of an Oracle database’s control file, data files and archive logs; it copies them to an Oracle Cloud Infrastructure bucket or somewhere on the local

⁷Quoted from the output of RMAN’s `RESTORE DATABASE PREVIEW SUMMARY` command.

filesystem; it supports transparent symmetric-key encryption and decryption; it allows listing and deleting available backups as well as downloading a backup for recovery purposes.

The tool is implemented using the Python language and therefore its main interface is the Python script `cloud_backup.py` (although it is possible to use it as a library). The script works together with several other commands and external systems:

- OracleDB's `sqlplus`, for listing data files used by the database;
- the `df` command, for determining filesystems used by the data files;
- the `sapi` CLI tool, for listing available filesystem snapshots;
- OracleDB's `rman`, for many tasks related to DB backup & restore;
- `rclone`, a versatile tool for cloud-agnostic file transfers;
- Oracle's Object Storage buckets, for storing cloud backups immutably.

The CLI interface follows the design of `git` by splitting functionality in subcommands and allowing for customization with required or optional flags. Available subcommands are `create`, `list`, `download` and `delete`. Any operation requires specifying on which particular database (`DB_NAME`) and Oracle installation (`ORACLE_HOME`) the tool should work on: this information is passed in using command-line flags `--db-name` and `--oracle-home`. Other flags exist for configuring much of the tool's behaviour. A typical invocation is given below (sensitive information has been replaced with `'*'`):

```
$ ./cloud_backup.py \
  --db-name="BKPTTEST2" \
  --oracle-home="/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms19170_cern2" \
  --rman-credentials="*****/*****@rman" \
  --destination="oci" \
  --oci-bucket="database-copies" \
  --oci-endpoint="https://[...].oci.customer-oci.com" \
  --oci-customer-access-key="*****" \
  --oci-customer-secret-key="*****" \
  --encryption \
  --encryption-password="*****" \
  --encryption-salt="*****" \
  create
```

The full list of subcommands and command-line flags together with their respective descriptions can be displayed using the `--help` flag.

3.1 Creating a Cloud Backup

The most complex operation implemented by the `cloud_backup` tool is the creation of a backup. The following paragraphs describe the steps performed when `cloud_backup.py` is run with subcommand `create`.

First, the database's data files are listed using an SQL query performed through Oracle's `sqlplus`. Each returned path is run through `df` to determine the filesystem that contains it; duplicates are removed. The available snapshots of each filesystem are listed using `sapi`. An algorithm selects an appropriate set of snapshots, one from each filesystem, making sure they are not too spread apart in time. The data files' paths within each selected snapshot are determined and collected in a list; the most recent snapshot's time serves as the proposed recovery time for a potential recovery in case of disaster.

Now that a list of data files was computed, the tool determines the required archive logs to include in the backup to ensure a successful recovery. It does that by cataloging⁸ the data files and asking RMAN to perform a restore preview summary. The archive logs returned by the `rman` command are augmented by an additional time window of archive logs for additional safety. The returned data files paths are also checked to ensure they all reside in the selected filesystem snapshots.

A recovery also needs a control file and a parameter file to initialize the database. Both are generated at this point using RMAN. Additionally, a `metadata.json` file is written to disk, containing various information potentially useful at recovery time.

Next, all files determined/generated above are sent to the cloud using `rclone`. The backup receives an identifier based on its creation time. Within the OCI bucket, backups are namespaced by the `DB_NAME` of the database from which they were created. Figure 5 shows a web view into the bucket's contents after two backups were created for database `BKPTTEST2`.

3.2 Code Structure

The `main` function in `cloud_backup.py` serves as the tool's entry-point. It uses Python's `argparse`⁹ standard library module to parse the command-line arguments. The functionality is divided into several subcommands: `create`, `list`, `delete` and `download`.

Global command-line flags, which apply to all commands, are set on the `parser` object. Subcommand-specific flags are set on the appropriate `parser_*` object. Each such object sets a *handler* function to be called in case the corresponding subcommand is selected. Handlers are always

⁸Oracle documentation: „Managing a Recovery Catalog”

⁹Module `argparse` in the Python documentation.

Figure 5: Oracle’s Object Storage web UI showing the bucket contents

called `run` and `live` in separate files (for example, the handler for the `create` command resides in `cmd_create.py`).

Another file, `utils.py`, implements generic functionality needed in more than one command, such as interacting with RMAN (class `RMAN`) and interacting with `rclone` (class `Rclone`).

3.3 Rclone

File transfers are done using `rclone`¹⁰, a tool similar to `rsync` that can transfer files between many types of *remotes*. These can be cloud object storage providers (like AWS’s S3 or OCI’s OOS), storage servers (WebDAV, FTP, SMB etc.) or simply the local filesystem. Additionally, `rclone` allows „wrapping” these remotes in special-purpose remotes that transparently provide specific functionality before/after file transfers (such as encryption¹¹, compression¹¹ or chunking of large files¹¹).

`Rclone` remotes are normally configured using the special configuration file `~/.config/rclone/rclone.conf`. This is where the `rclone` config command writes configuration and where all `rclone *` commands expect to find it at runtime. However, `rclone` also allows on-the-fly remote configuration using environment variables¹². This featured can be seen in action in file `utils.py`, class `Rclone`, method `__init__`.

`Rclone` supports many generic commands that it „translates” into remote-specific network messages/API calls: `copy` and `copyto` for transferring files and directories; `ls`, `lsd` and `lsjson` for listing remote files and directories;

¹⁰ `Rclone` is a command-line program to manage files on cloud storage.

¹¹ „Wrapper” remotes: `crypt`, `compress` and `chunker`.

¹² Configuration using environment variables.

`delete` and `purge` for deleting files; and many others¹³.

3.4 Support for Encryption

As mentioned in the *rclone* section, special remotes exist for adding transparent functionality on top of file transfers. One such „wrapper” remote is `crypt`¹¹, which encrypts files before upload and decrypts them after download without requiring any changes in command usage. It uses a symmetric-key encryption algorithm. The required password and salt can also be configured by environment variables, as can be seen in `Rclone.__init__`.

3.5 Local Backups

For testing purposes one might want to prepare a backup but store it locally instead of sending it to the cloud. The tool provides a `--destination` flag, with options `oci` and `local`. Additional flags should be provided depending on the chosen destination.

Encryption and backup destination are orthogonal concepts. One can save, locally or to the cloud, backups that are encrypted or not. This can be done by mixing the appropriate flags.

3.6 Possible Improvements

Over the course of development many ideas occurred to us that could improve the project in one way or another. This is a short list:

- Add file compression using *rclone*’s `compress`¹¹ remote. This would reduce cloud costs for both storage and egress network bandwidth.
- Allow resuming backup transfers. Currently, each `create` command prepares and uploads a backup starting from scratch. This is fine for small backup sizes, but in multi-terabyte scenarios the approach falls short, especially since retention rules will prevent the deletion of incomplete backups for a long time. To be able to continue backup transfers, a „stable” backup identifier should be devised (instead of the current timestamp as it is implemented now); then subsequent `create` commands would try uploading to the same bucket prefix.

4 Conclusions

We have presented the design and implementation of the `cloud_backup` tool in the context of data protection challenges at CERN. We believe *immutable buckets* can be an appropriate solution in setups where data preservation is crucial and access boundaries of existing tooling are not sufficient.

¹³Full list of *rclone* commands.

We've shown backing up to immutable buckets in the cloud is viable for Oracle databases. However, our backup solution is database-agnostic in all aspects related to file transfer. Adapting it to PostgreSQL or MySQL only requires rewriting the logic that selects the relevant database files on the filesystem.